

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES.

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Annotation: *The development of the world cannot be imagined without foreign languages. As the process of globalization accelerates, the demand for learning of foreign language is growing. Especially, English has become a common requirement to become a mature professional in any field. This article will provide methods to use in learning a foreign language.*

Key words and expressions: *foreign languages, methods, learning process, language skills, vocabulary, grammar.*

What is the secret of effective learning a foreign language and being able to speak it quickly? This question makes more learners think over and over. Why is it so? When most students who have been learning a foreign language for three or four years cannot speak it fluently, meanwhile another student who has been performing well spending three or four hours a week for learning the language. As a result of the research it has been shown that this is due to the interest and approach to the language organization. In fact, learning a foreign language is not as complicated a concept as we think, but the easiest way to learn a foreign language is based on a personal preference. Language learning will be efficient and fun when we start it with great interest and enthusiasm.

As in any field, the most important aspect in the organization of a language is motivation. Moreover, we must always think about why we are learning the language, a purpose and how to approach to its organization. Another most crucial thing is to gain self-confidence in learning of language. Only then, we can take a serious step in improving the language learning process.

Nowadays, many language courses offer two hours of study two or three days a week. This method is suitable for many students. However, some language learners deny this because everyone's approach to language organization is different. For instance, someone improves with daily repetition and someone else learns in other ways. I think, you need to learn it every day when you organize a foreign language. On the ground that as a result of daily repetition, the process of language organization is accelerated. Instead, two or three-day learners a week were distracted by breaks or other activities, as a result they practice less than daily learners. As a consequence, the process of language organization in them is much slower. Before you start learning a foreign language, make a daily commitment to yourself. For example, you can say "I spend 1 or 2 hours every day learning English". If you follow this, your memory will also increase dramatically.

Language learning is a time-consuming and laborious process, whether it occurs in an authentic or an organized context. Children usually acquire their first language from 2 to 5 ages to achieve full grammatical competence [5, 23], during which time they are exposed to massive amounts of input. The same is undoubtedly true of second language acquisition. If learners do not receive exposure to the target language, they cannot acquire it [1, 3].

Linguists have divided the organization of language into 4 major areas:

- Reading -the ability to understand a text read in a foreign language
- Listening- the ability to understand a text heard in a foreign language
- Writing – the ability to write in a foreign language
- Speaking – the ability to express one's thoughts in a foreign language

To achieve these 4 things, it is important for the reader to master grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. Initially, the learning of a foreign language begins with the organization of grammar. As you know, grammar has a lot of tenses, mispronounced verbs and thousands of rules. The big problem is to memorize them which scares students. Many students do not have difficulty in memorizing rules but do not know where to use them. Firstly, organizing grammar does not mean

memorizing a rule but being able to put that mastered rule into practice. The question of how to these rules can be easily remembered is of interest to everyone.

As Reiss says, not each of the learners will orientate studying grammar so strongly. Some younger learners may tend to look at a language functionally - as a tool for communicating, not only memorizing, - and may be less able to benefit from grammar instruction. Nonetheless, personally I consider that many successful learners are not only prepared to focus on form but actively seek to practice. For such learners, a “communicative” syllabus that eschews a focus on grammar may be missing the mark [2, 38].

Secondly, you have to do is work harder on each rule and find examples that fit the rule. If the memorized rule does not apply in practice, it’s like buying a book and not reading it.

First of all, choose the most important topics when organizing grammar. Then, take 10 days for each topic and organize every topic more deeply. As a result, you will learn a foreign language in a short time.

Moreover, the purpose of learning any language is to be able to speak that language. The most beneficial features in the formation of oral speech are vocabulary richness and pronunciation. Most people understand every word in English when they say word memorization. No, it is not. However, it is enough to memorize the most common words in English because not all words are used in oral speech. Which method is more useful in word memorization? First of all, when you memorize a word in English, make 5 sentences for each word you memorize. Another convenient way to memorize a word is to read more in a learned foreign language. Due to the fact that as you read, unfamiliar words come out. Then you should mark these words, search the dictionary and write them down in a notebook. Do not try to memorize these words by force because you cannot learn anything by force. On the other hand, if you read text on a topic that interests you every day and write unfamiliar words, it will be easier to remember. This is because the brain remembers important information quickly. That’s why even words you do not know on a topic you are interested in are automatically stored in your mind. A text that is

read in a foreign language is very useful not only in memorizing words but also in repeating grammatical topics.

The second successful method of learning vocabulary was explained by American scientist Tim Ferris, author of the book “The 4-Hour Workweek” he explains the secret of language organization as follows: "Three months are enough to understand 90 % of a desired foreign language, but it takes 3 years to understand 95%". From this theory, it would not be wrong to say that language depends more on the learner [4, 23].

Furthermore, each language has its own pronunciation. According to linguists, there are more than 150 sounds in total, and each language uses an average of 30 sounds [3, 34]. Generally, pronunciation needs to be improved after learning a foreign language fluency. The easiest way to improve pronunciation is to listen more in a foreign language. It is necessary to watch movies in this language, to listen to songs. When you hear a song in a foreign language, working with the text, that is translating it or writing transcript will also help your vocabulary. These words are stored in your mind along with the songs.

I think, learners have at least some knowledge about how to learn a foreign language. So, when learning a foreign language, it is necessary to pay attention to every aspect of it. In this way, good results can be achieved by using above-mentioned methods. Apart from, organizing a foreign language highly depends on the student rather than the training centers and teachers. In addition, the rightly chosen methodology, confidence and passion are enough to acquire a foreign language.

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